

Chemical speciation and determination of antimony with *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine and brilliant green in an acidic non-ionic micellar media

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The individual forms of antimony, i.e. antimony(III), antimony(V) and total antimony in fresh ground water and in industrial effluents have been determined spectrophotometrically. The method is based on extraction of chloroantimonate(V) complex in 0.5–7.5 M HCl acid medium in the presence of a non-ionic surfactant TX-100 with *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (DPBA) in toluene and subsequent reaction of the extracts with brilliant green (BG) at 1.0–3.0 pH. The molar absorptivity of the $\text{Sb}^{\text{V}}\text{-Cl}^--(\text{TX-100})\text{-DPBA}\text{-BG}$ complex in toluene is $1.83 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 640 nm. The detection limit of the method is 10 ppb.

Many spectrophotometric methods^{1–7} have been reported for the determination of antimony in a variety of complex materials. Among these the classical iodide method¹ is widely used for spectrophotometric determination antimony. Fluorone derivatives, such as 2,6,7-trihydroxy-9-[4-(8-hydroxy-5-quinolylozophenyl)]fluorone², 9-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-2,3,7-trihydroxyfluorone³ have been reported for the determination of antimony. Some other reagents, viz. sodium dodecylsulphate and polyethoxyethanol⁴, phenyltetrazolium chloride⁵, and azo dye of benzimidazole series⁶ have also been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of antimony.

The present investigation describes selective extraction of antimony as its hexachloroantimonate(V) complex, in presence of a non-ionic surfactant TX-100 into toluene, with *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (DPBA) and the extract is equilibrated with brilliant green for colour development. Nine surfactants, DPBA and its six derivatives and three basic dyes have been examined at an acidity of 6 M HCl. By the extraction of hexachloro complex of antimony in presence of TX-100 with DPBA and colour development with BG, the method becomes extremely selective as most of the common ions associated with antimony in water samples do not interfere. Moreover, this method enhances the sensitivity as compared to classical brilliant green method. The present method has been applied for the speciation and determination of antimony(III), antimony(V) and total antimony at ppb level in groundwater and in effluents originated from various industrial activities.

Results and Discussion

Hexachloroantimonate(V) in presence of a non-ionic surfactant TX-100 was extracted with DPBA into toluene over 6 M HCl. The extract was made chromogenic by equilibrating it with the basic dye brilliant green. The photometric properties were found to be enhanced than the

classical dye method, such as those based on the SbCl_6^- -dye and SbCl_6^- -DPBA-dye into toluene.

Oxidants like ceric ammonium sulphate (CAS), sodium nitrate, peroxide and permanganate were examined for the oxidation of antimony(III). Except CAS, all rendered high blank absorbance, hence CAS was selected. A 1–3 ml of 0.01 M (6.4%, w/v) solution of CAS was adequate for maximum oxidation.

Extraction of antimony(V) :

The extraction of SbCl_6^- was performed with *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine into a number of organic polar and non-polar solvents, such as benzene, toluene, chloroform, isobutylmethyl ketone, 1-pentanol and ethyl acetate in an acidic non-ionic surfactant (TX-100) media. The extraction was found to be quantitative (96.3–99.4%) with the various tested solvents.

Among the various solvents used only benzene ($\epsilon_{640} = 1.90 \times 10^5$) and toluene ($\epsilon_{640\text{nm}} = 1.83 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were the most sensitive after their reaction with brilliant green. Carbon tetrachloride gave incomplete extraction whereas other solvents extracted excess dye.

Lower extractability of the complex was observed when sulphuric acid was used. This might have been caused by the formation of unextractable sulphato-complex. The optimum acidity range for full extraction of the complex was found in the range 5.5–7.5 M HCl.

The molar absorptivity values of the extract with brilliant green for 7 various amidines differed significantly from each other with respect to substitutions of +I and –I inductive effect causing groups. The methyl group (+I) was found more sensitive than chloro group. The sensitivity pattern for CH_3 group was in the order $o > m > p$, while reverse was the case with Cl group. However, the parent

compound *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine was found to be the most sensitive among all and hence was selected. The extract, when reacted with brilliant green, a molar absorptivity range of $(1.58-1.83) \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for 7 amidines was found (Table 1). A maximum extraction and complete colour development of the complex occurred at a level of $(0.1-1.0) \times 10^{-2} M$ DPBA.

Table 1. Spectral characteristics of $[(\text{SbCl}_6)\text{TX-100}]^-$ complex with various amidines and brilliant green

Amidine	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{R}$ $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{N}-\text{H}$	$\epsilon^*, \times 10^5$ dm^3 $\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$
R		
<i>N,N'</i> -Diphenylbenzamidine	C_6H_5	1.83
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -(2-methylphenyl)benzamidine	2- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	1.78
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -(3-methylphenyl)benzamidine	3- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	1.74
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -(4-methylphenyl)benzamidine	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	1.70
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -(2-chlorophenyl)benzamidine	2- ClC_6H_4	1.58
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -(3-chlorophenyl)benzamidine	3- ClC_6H_4	1.62
<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -(4-chlorophenyl)benzamidine	4- ClC_6H_4	1.66

*Molar absorptivity values calculated at absorption maximum of 640 nm

The extraction of antimony complex was carried out in presence of 2 anionic, 5 cationic and 2 non-ionic surfactants. Of these, the anionic surfactants rendered high blank absorbance due to extraction of excessive dye. Good sensitivities were observed with cationic and non-ionic surfactants. The molar absorptivity values of the antimony complex with brilliant green in presence of various surfactants were found in the range $(1.30-1.83) \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 640 nm (Table 2). For complete extraction and maximum absorbance of the complex $(1.0-4.0) \times 10^{-4} M$ TX-100 was found adequate.

Table 2. Spectral data of chloroantimonate(v) complex with DPBA in presence of brilliant green and various surfactants

Surfactant	$\epsilon^*, \times 10^5$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$
<i>Anionic</i> :	
Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)	Dye extracted in reagent blank
Lithium lauryl sulphate (LLS)	Dye extracted in reagent blank
<i>Cationic</i> :	
Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB)	1.46
Cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC)	1.50
Cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide (CDEAB)	1.40
Hexadecyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTAC)	1.44
Tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide (TTAB)	1.30
<i>Non-ionic</i> :	
Polyoxyethylenediisobutylphenol (TX-100)	1.83
Polyoxyethylenedodecylether (Brij-35)	1.42

*Molar absorptivity values calculated at absorption maximum of 640 nm.

Colour reaction of the extract with dye :

The various basic dyes, viz. brilliant green, malachite green and crystal violet were tested for the coloration of the organic extract at pH 1.0-3.0. These basic dyes are not ex-

tracted by the organic solvent used in the system. The colour reaction of the basic dye cation on the extract was found to be quantitative and the dye cation takes the place of DPBA. Among the various basic dyes used, the brilliant green (BG) imparted fairly intense colour to the organic extract. The reagent blank showed small absorbance ($A = 0.04$) at the absorption maximum of 640 nm.

The absorption spectra of $\text{Sb}^{\text{V}}\text{-Cl}^-(\text{TX-100})$ complex with various amidines, $\text{Sb}^{\text{V}}\text{-Cl}^-$ -DPBA with various surfactants and of $\text{Sb}^{\text{V}}\text{-Cl}^-$ -DPBA in toluene against the respective reagent blank and reagent blank against toluene were scanned after colour development of the extract with brilliant green at $\text{pH } 2.0 \pm 0.2$. All these systems exhibited an absorption maximum around 640 nm. The absorption maximum of 640 nm remained unaffected when the concentration of Sb^{V} was varied. The absorption spectra of $\text{Sb}^{\text{V}}\text{-Cl}^-(\text{TX-100})\text{-DPBA/BG}$ complex in toluene and the reagent blank against toluene were recorded. The reagent blank exhibited some absorbance value ($A = 0.04$) at 640 nm. Therefore, it was needed to prepare a reference in all absorbance measurement.

Tests performed with varying concentrations of aqueous solutions containing BG showed that $(0.3-3.0) \times 10^{-3} M$ BG are required for maximum colour formation. In practice, $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ aqueous BG solution was used throughout the experiment.

In the complexation reaction system, the organic extract upon reaction with cationic dye BG^+ gave an amidine (HA) replaced complex⁷. Curve-fitting method was used to determine the molar ratio of antimony to BG. A $\log M$ vs $\log D$ plot indicated the formation of a 1 : 2, $\text{Sb}^{\text{V}} : \text{BG}$ ion-pair complex. The most probable reaction mechanism can be expressed as

where, $[\text{SbCl}_6]^-$ is anionic chloro complex of antimony, abbreviations HA and BG^+ denote amidine and cationic brilliant green and the subscript 'o' expresses the organic phase, respectively.

The system adhered to the Beer's law up to $0.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Sb^{V} with Pearson's correlation coefficient value of 0.999. The complex $\text{Sb}^{\text{V}}\text{-Cl}^-(\text{TX-100})\text{-DPBA/BG}$ in toluene has the absorbance and molar absorptivity values of 0.450 ± 0.005 and $(1.83 \pm 0.02) \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 640 nm respectively, at 95% confidence level. The present method is applicable for detection of a minimum of $0.01 \mu\text{g Sb}^{\text{V}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ (or 10 ppb).

Linear least-square method was applied to prepare the calibration curve for direct determination of antimony in real samples. The precision evaluation of the method was made by 10 replicate determinations of Sb at a level of $0.3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and the relative standard deviation of the method was found to be 1.5%.

Effect of diverse ions :

A large number of foreign cations and anions were tested towards the selectivity of the present method. Incremental amounts of individual diverse ions were added during the determination of 0.3 µg Sb ml⁻¹ as in the proposed method. The interference of Au^{III} and Tl^{III} can be eliminated by masking with thiourea and EDTA respectively. The tolerable amounts (in parentheses, mg) of various diverse ions causing error in absorbance of the complex less than ±2% are as follows : Tl^I (0.11, in presence of 1 ml 1% w/v EDTA); thiourea (0.5); Sn^{IV} (0.6); Ag^I (1.0); Hg^{II}, Mo^{VI} (1.2); Fe^{III}, Cu^{II} (1.5); Cd^{II}, Se^{IV}, Pb^{II}, Zr^{IV}, W^{VI} (2.0); As^{III} (4.0); Th^{IV} (5.0); Ti^{IV}, V^V (5.5); citrate (6.0); Bi^{III} (10); Mn^{II} (15); Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Al^{III}, Ca^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, EDTA, Sr^{II}, tartarate, phosphate (20); Cr^{III} (40); fluoride, nitrate (45) and oxalate (50).

Application : The method was applied for the speciation and determination of Sb in various water samples. For the determination of total antimony, Sb^{III} was oxidised to Sb^V with ceric ammonium sulphate, without involving oxidation step. The difference of the two gave the value for Sb^{III}. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Determination of antimony in different water samples

Sample*	AAS method µg dm ⁻³	Present method (µg dm ⁻³)		
		Total Sb (RSD)**	Sb ^V (RSD)**	Sb ^{III}
S1	81.5	80.0 (1.1)	13.0 (1.2)	67.0
S2	114.3	113.0 (1.2)	16.6 (1.1)	96.4
S3	26.3	26.6 (1.3)	20.0 (1.1)	6.6
S4	60.3	63.3 (1.2)	10.0 (1.3)	53.3
S5	88.5	86.6 (1.1)	13.3 (1.2)	73.3
S6	66.0	66.6 (1.3)	-	-
S7	136.0	133.3 (1.3)	-	-

*S1 = Tube well water of Kota ward of Raipur city, S2 = effluent of Govt. dairy, Kumhari, Durg, S3 = effluent of DMC Alum Plant, Kumhari, S4 = effluent of rice mill, Gondia, Maharashtra, S5 = anode paste plant effluent, BALCO, Korba, S6 = aluminium plant effluent, BALCO, S7 = effluent of Kedia Distillery, Kumhari, M.P., India

**Relative standard deviation value (five measurements made).

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss-Jena SPEKOL spectrophotometer equipped with 1-cm quartz cells and a Systronic 335 pH meter were used.

A stock solution of antimony was prepared by dissolv-

ing antimony metal (99.9%; 0.100 g) in concentrated H₂SO₄ (15 ml) by heating over a hot water-bath and the resulting solution was diluted to 1 litre with 1 M HCl containing 0.1% (w/v) tartaric acid to get the desired solution. A 0.15% (w/v) solution of *N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine in organic solvent and a 0.06% (w/v) brilliant green solution in double-distilled water were employed. 10 M HCl acid was used for acidity adjustment. A 0.1% (w/v) surfactant solution in double-distilled water was used. All chemicals used were of analytical grade (Glaxo/Merck/SD finechem).

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution containing up to 6 µg of Sb^{III}, were added 1 ml each of ceric ammonium sulphate (6.4%, w/v) and TX-100 (1%, w/v). The acidity of the final 10 ml aqueous solution was maintained at 6 M HCl with hydrochloric acid (10 M). The excess oxidizing ceric ion was removed by dropwise addition of hydroxylammonium hydrochloride (1%, w/v) until the solution became colourless. The aqueous solution was then equilibrated with toluene solution of DPBA (0.15%; 10 ml) for 1 min. The lower aqueous layer was discarded and the upper organic layer retained for determination. The above toluene extract was again equilibrated at pH 2.0 ± 0.5 with brilliant green solution (0.06%; 5 ml) for 1 min. The aqueous layer was again rejected and the organic layer drained and dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate, ≈2 g).

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